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Artificial Intelligence and Children Evangelism: Opportunities and Pitfalls

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Abstract

This paper is focused on Artificial Intelligence and Children Evangelism: Opportunities and Pitfalls. The discourse examined AI, what AI connotes and its roles in children's evangelism. The main benefits of AI were examined and discussed thus: AI is used to create stunning images of biblical characters and events. At the same time, children's teachers can have favourable circumstances to connect with their communities online. In addition, some benefits of using Artificial Intelligence were also itemized and discussed such as providing unique opportunities for discipleship and evangelism, especially for children. The paper also expatiates on children evangelism strategies using AI. It was recommended in the paper among other things that ethical considerations for Artificial Intelligence must be employed in order not to expose children to mental and moral harms. That is, unrestricted access to digital technology brings risks to children's well-being both mental and physical health, and as a result, close monitoring is required when children engage with social media. Similarly, wider evangelization can only be achieved through the use of AI as house-to-house evangelism may not be enough to win many souls.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Evangelism, Children, Opportunities and Pitfalls

Introduction

Evangelization is a task and mission commissioned by Christ to the Church as an institution (Matt. 24:14). An effective way to meet up with the task and mission of modern evangelization, is through social media. Social media is increasingly becoming a part of everyday life for many people including children which can invariably be an effective tool for children's evangelism. Social media has become an integral part of many children, teenagers, and youth lives. The children normally use social interactions with others essentially with the people around them, like parents, teachers, and peers.

Social media refers to websites and applications where users can create ideas, share information, or participate in social networking. Any Web site that allows social interaction is considered a social media site, including social networking sites such as Facebook, MySpace, and Twitter; gaming sites and virtual worlds such as Club Penguin, Second Life, and the Sims; video sites such as YouTube; and blogs. These types of interaction have grown bigger over time (O'Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011). Sociology group (2023) believes that social media, apart from the interaction, it also allows users to share information, chat with other people, share their opinions, create content, and embrace their differences. Most children are exposed to wrong content on social media using different types of AI innovations such as ChatGPT, Facebook, Siri, Alexa, Google Assistant, Cortana, IBM and so on. The explosion of artificial intelligence comes with many benefits and challenges, especially for children who are heavily interacting with the different types of the innovative.

As long as AI is used in a way that is appropriate and responsible, it can also be as an effective tool for spreading the gospel (the good tidings), especially for children.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think and learn like humans. Godkulture Team (2023) believed that AI involves creating algorithms and systems that can process information, recognize patterns, make decisions, solve problems, and even understand language. AI is something that has exploded over the past couple of years. AI is everywhere and it's transforming the way children learn, engage, and even socialize. AI is already central to children's digital environment, through recommendation algorithms or automated decision-making systems. Generative AI will no doubt take an even greater hold of their digital experiences, and at a rapid pace.

Ofcom's Statistical Release Calendar (2023) reported that almost eight in ten children aged 3-17 (79%) used apps or sites for messaging or voice/ video calls. However, in common with many other media activities, this varied by age, from 48% of children aged 3-4 to 98% of 12-17-year-olds. Two in three (64%) children aged 3-17 used apps for social media, while a third (32%) used apps or sites to post videos they had made, and 15% live-streamed their content. More information on these activities is explored below in 'Girls and Boys'. Three-quarters of children aged 8-17 (72%) played games online.

Digital Technology is an unstoppable force that is shaping modern life, without the exception of children's cycles. With a digital world at their fingertips, children with access to technology have seemingly endless opportunities for play, learning, civic engagement, and social interactions (UNICEF, 2024). Mark Finley (2024) defines digital evangelism as the systematic and intentional use of internet platforms to spread the gospel to the online population. The goal is to introduce people to Christ and then connect them to a church family. In today's digital age, children can learn effectively from online Christian platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, TikTok, Snapchat, and more which have emerged as powerful tools for communication and connectivity. Any individual, group, and likes using YouTube, Google, Facebook, and other social media platforms, are already using AI.

Children's evangelism on social media is primarily to connect with different groups of children in millions for the purpose of the salvation of their souls, growth, and connectivity. This is in line with Kidder (2016) who believes that social media creates highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated content. Consider social media not only as a two-way engagement but as something that can include millions of people.

As technology continues to develop, the church must continue to adapt to strategically place the gospel where people will find and hear it. The purpose of reaching children with the gospel, is in the fulfillment of Jesus's words, said, "And this gospel of the kingdom shall be preached in all the world for a witness unto all nations; and then the end shall come" (Matthew 24:14). Christ's end-time message can be rapidly spread around the world in seconds. As social media becomes an increasingly popular channel for connecting and communicating with mass audiences of a younger generation, the community of children should not be left behind (Wiedemann, 2022).

However, Christian teachers, mentors, and educators that are now involving in the use of AI (and all technology), must align with a deeper understanding of God's purpose for all people and nations without any discrimination. Digital media is a tool to reach millions of children, not an end in itself. It is not how many children we can gather to follow the church programmes but it is the sincere numbers of them that have a genuine encounter with God.

Types of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be categorized based on its capabilities and functionalities (IBM Consultancy, 2024):

1. **Narrow AI (Weak AI):** Designed to perform a specific task, such as facial recognition, language translation, or playing chess. Most AI systems today are narrow AI, excelling in one area but lacking general intelligence.
2. **General AI (Strong AI):** A more advanced form of AI that aims to replicate human cognitive abilities, enabling machines to perform any intellectual task that a human can do. This type of AI remains largely theoretical at present.
3. **Artificial Superintelligence (ASI):** This is a hypothetical form of AI that surpasses human intelligence in all aspects, including creativity, wisdom, and social skills. ASI would have its own beliefs, desires, and emotions.

AI is built using various subfields, including:

Machine Learning (ML): AI systems that learn from data and improve over time without explicit programming.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): Allows machines to understand, interpret, and respond to human language.

Computer Vision: Enabling machines to interpret and understand visual information from the world.

Robotics: Involves creating robots that can perform tasks autonomously, often using AI for decision-making.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study draws on three key theories: Technological Determinism theory, The Theory of Developmental Psychology, and Theological Pedagogy which explores the intersection of technology, theology, and child development. These theories help to contextualize the impact of AI on children's spiritual education and evangelism.

i. Technological Determinism Theory

Technological determinism is a branch of determinism in sociology coined by the American economist and sociologist Thorstein Veblen (1857-1929). In the words of Smith (1994) cited by Gill Singh (2024), technological determinism can be summarized as "Technology decides history." He asserted that our lives including the children and youth to a great extent, revolve around our smartphones and tablets connected continuously on a daily basis throughout the week to the internet. It's so encompassing in this modern age that it is now replacing physical interaction as the preferred mode of interaction.

The Technology Determinism Theory suggests that technology shapes societal structures and human behaviour, often independently of other factors. This theory underscores the inevitability of AI's influence on evangelistic methods and tools. AI-driven platforms, such as chatbots, virtual reality (VR), and gamified learning, offer engaging ways to communicate biblical truths to children. AI can tailor content to individual learning styles and cultural contexts, making it more impactful.

ii. The Theory of Developmental Psychology

Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development (1896-1980) and Erik Erikson's psychosocial stage theory are considered some of the most influential psychologists of the twentieth century, and their stages theory of cognitive development revolutionized the view of children's thinking and learning (Arduini-Van Hoose, 2022). Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development and Erik Erikson's psychosocial stages are particularly relevant in understanding how AI can align with a child's spiritual growth. Developmental psychology provides insights into how children process information, form beliefs, and develop moral reasoning to guide them throughout their life span. It also looks at how these thought processes influence how we understand and interact with the world. AI can adapt to various developmental stages by offering age-appropriate

lessons. For example, younger children might benefit from interactive storytelling, while older children could explore theological debates through AI-facilitated discussions.

iii. Theological Pedagogy

Theological pedagogy emphasizes the role of teaching and learning in spiritual formation. It integrates biblical principles with effective communication strategies. AI can enhance theological pedagogy by creating immersive experiences, such as virtual Bible adventures or personalized devotional prompts. AI can also assist teachers in tracking children's spiritual progress and tailoring discipleship strategies.

Media for Interaction

Research done by Communication apps and sites provides an array of different opportunities for children to interact with others online, including messaging and calling, social media, online gaming, posting videos on VSPs, and live-streaming content. AI has been a part of children's lives long before now. AI is more prevalent than most children, or even adults, realize. Children use AI for homework help, AI interaction which is children's direct engagement with AI agents, where the children ask questions and seek information (this area of AI can have a positive impact on children because it significantly broadens children's access to knowledge and information). AI algorithms suggest the next videos to play, based on a child's viewing history. Social media is all about relationships, community, and content, and since the children are aware of these strategies, it has a great opportunity to tell others about the salvation of mankind. AI has come to stay and gradually forming some connection with children, and some children are seeing AI as a source of companionship. This is the more reason why the use of social media for evangelism is advisable because it is all about building relationships which is more appropriate than AI companionship.

Effective Social Media Platforms for Children Evangelism

The concept of social media platforms is a globalized issue that will give access to people, communities, and tribes who would otherwise never step foot in a church or engage intentionally in a meaningful relationship with the Christian. According to various research, engaging in multiple forms of social media has been shown to benefit children. There are many kinds of social media, including Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and the likes, each of these sites has several opportunities for witnessing and evangelizing.

1. **YouTube (video content):** This can be useful for video content, where the children teachers/pastors can record the sermons and then upload them. An interesting way of using the channel is to ask members for testimonies. Many will be inspired by how God intervened in the everyday lives of church members.
2. **Instagram (visual storytelling):** This allows everyone including the children with the assistance of their parents or guidance to upload pictures, visual storytelling, and videos of church-related activities, especially the children's activities. It will show the true life of the church. Anyone can take pictures/ videos to be uploaded onto Instagram with the assistance of the parents and guardians.
3. **Facebook (groups and pages):** this is a perfect place to evangelize. This can be used to post pictures of all kinds of activities in which children can engage.
4. **TikTok (short-form videos):** Utilizing various forms of media such as images, a small videos, posts, and podcasts can also enhance engagement. It is very effective with minimal costs.
5. **Snaphat (ephemeral content):** such content could include inspirational Bible verses or devotional reflections which can help the spiritual growth of the audiences.
6. **Twitter:** It can be created by the children's teachers as a way to communicate with the children and youth. It also can serve as direct traffic to the church blog and Web sites.
7. Online gaming communities.

Opportunities/Benefits of Using Social Media for Children Evangelism

Social media in our modern world; enlarges the circle of believers' influence irrespective of their cultural background, Christian sect, languages, and countries. Ogbole (2024) believed that AI as a technology can process massive amounts of data, engage with people at a personal level, and automate tasks that would otherwise take years for humans to accomplish. The following are the possibilities for the use of social media:

1. **Wider Reach and Accessibility:** AI-powered platforms can help evangelists connect with people including children globally, regardless of language barriers or time zones. Using tools like chatbots, AI can engage with individuals in their preferred language and provide them with personalized biblical resources. Social media creates communities of people from various backgrounds who share common interests. People with the same interests connect more with each other. Digital evangelism beams the message into people's homes wherever they are, in whatever country they are in, in the context of their language and culture.
2. **Efficiency and Cost-effectiveness:** AI can automate many of the repetitive tasks associated with evangelism, such as answering common questions or providing Bible study materials, freeing up more time for personal human interactions. AI-driven tools reduce the need for extensive physical resources, such as printed materials or large-scale in-person events. Churches and ministries can allocate resources more efficiently, ensuring a wider impact with less expense. In a sense AI can help Christians make the most of every opportunity in accordance with (Ephesians 5:16- "Redeeming the time, because the days are evil") in spreading the gospel. This targeted approach ensures that resources are used efficiently and that evangelistic efforts are directed toward those most in need of spiritual guidance.
3. **Social Media Evangelism:** AI can analyze social media trends and data to identify people who might be open to hearing the gospel. It provides unique opportunities for discipleship and evangelism.
4. **Overcoming Physical Limitations and Barriers:** If we want to reach a global audience and penetrate previously unreached people, global technology provides a powerful platform to accomplish God's mission. The Christian body can overcome physical limitations and barriers, especially in war zone areas and other religious sects that are opposed to the gospel of our Lord Jesus Christ.
5. **Increased Engagement and Interactive Content:** With AI-driven content and chatbots, children can engage with the gospel at their own pace, asking questions and receiving answers in a personalized manner. AI can tailor evangelism content to individual children's needs. This engagement leads to deeper discipleship and spiritual growth. This will invariably increase positive communication, social connection, and technical skills of the children, especially providing a lifeline for isolated kids to interact with friends and peers.
6. **Global Impact:** AI enables ministries to reach children in remote areas and unreached children groups that would otherwise be inaccessible due to geography, language, or political barriers. This set of children will enjoy equal access to evangelism. Through this, the church will fulfil the biblical mandate to "preach the gospel to all creation" (Mark 16:15).
7. **Digital Technology** can open doors for learning, community, jobs, and services for children often excluded by location, poverty, discrimination, or emergency (UNICEF, 2024).
8. **More Souls Reached:** The ultimate profit in evangelism is the salvation of souls. AI allows for exponential outreach, meaning more people can hear the gospel and come to faith in Christ. The mind of God is that all should be saved and have eternal rest at the end of their journey on earth.
9. **Data Analysis:** AI can track engagement and understanding, helping refine evangelism strategies. This can assist human evangelists, freeing time for more personal connections.

Content Strategies for Children Evangelism on Social Media

Strategies for children's evangelism can take different forms, which include:

1. **Generating Images of Bible Characters and Scenes:** Enhance individual and collective creativity through developing and sharing Bible stories and teachings. AI can be used to create stunning images of biblical characters and events. Children are visual learners, and incorporating images in the form of animated videos and cartoons into your teaching can make the Bible more engaging and memorable. For instance, if you are teaching a sermon on the storyline of the Israelites crossing the Red Sea, AI can generate an image of them crossing the Red Sea by the help of Almighty God through his servant Moses. These images can enhance the preacher's sermon and help the children's congregation to visualize and internalize the stories in the Bible. AI-generated images can create colourful and engaging visuals for children's Bible stories. Since they are used to animation when they are watching their cartons, the generated images of different characters in the bible will be a better leverage for captivating the hearts, attention, and belief systems of the children. The present world is corrupt with deviant content and scenes like pornography, LGBTQ, violence, suicide missions and the like, the responsibility of the modern church is to arise and use the same contents positively as a saving grace for our innocent children.
2. **Use AI to Create Social Media Posts:** With the rise of social media, children's teachers can have a unique opportunity to connect with their communities online. Fostering of one's individual identity and unique social skills through Interactive live streams and Q&A sessions, sharing testimonies, and sharing memes and graphics. However, creating high-quality social media posts can take time and effort. AI can help optimize posts for different platforms and audiences and save time and resources.
3. **Create Content in Multiple Languages:** AI can help children's programmes translate their content into multiple languages. This will help break language barriers, expand their global outreach, and reach more people. However, it is essential to consider cultural and linguistic nuances to ensure the content is accurate and culturally sensitive. Editing is also essential to ensure that the translated content effectively conveys the intended message and values of the church.
4. **Personalized Learning and Engagement:** AI can create customized learning experiences for children, tailoring religious content to their interests, learning pace, and cognitive abilities. Interactive AI tools, such as chatbots or virtual assistants, could lead children through Bible stories, religious songs, and moral lessons in a fun and engaging way. This level of personalization helps hold children's attention and makes religious teachings more accessible.
5. **Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) in Religious Education:** AI-powered VR and AR technologies can create immersive, interactive experiences. For example, children can virtually experience Biblical events or walk through religious historical sites. These immersive experiences help bring religious stories and teachings to life, making them more engaging and memorable for young audiences.
6. **Accessibility and Global Reach:** AI-driven platforms like websites, apps, and social media can reach children in remote areas or those with limited access to physical churches. AI can help translate religious materials into different languages, making them accessible to children from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. This can facilitate global outreach and evangelism efforts in ways that would be impossible with traditional methods.
7. **Game-Based Learning:** AI can power educational games that teach religious principles through play. Games can be tailored to teach values such as kindness, honesty, and charity, as well as more specific religious teachings. Gamification, where children earn rewards for completing tasks, can make learning about faith more engaging and enjoyable.

8. **Safety and Moderation:** AI can be programmed to monitor and moderate online content, ensuring that children are exposed to age-appropriate religious material. This can help prevent harmful or misleading content and provide a safe space for children to explore religious ideas.

Nelson (2024) opined five (5) ways to increase engagement in children's ministry through social media:

1. **Use Real-life Pictures and Videos Whenever Possible:** Most people want to see authentic and faithful representations of the ministry. So as much as possible, the children's platform should share real-life pictures, personal testimonies, and videos on the ministry's social media accounts.
2. **Speak to the felt needs of the parents in your ministry, and let your social media serve their purpose, not yours:** focus on providing resources, encouragement, and support to parents as they navigate life and at-home discipleship.
3. **Post Consistently:** To avoid a vacuum and undertone of seriousness from the church organizer, there must be regular posting of content that will keep the children busy.
4. **Be Interactive:** The purpose of social media is for interaction. The page must be engaging, children and their parents frequently respond to your post. AI-powered games, videos, and chatbots can engage children in interactive and immersive experiences. Use Instagram Stories or Facebook polls to ask fun, thought-provoking questions related to Bible stories or upcoming events. Make it a priority to reply to comments and messages promptly
5. **Share Content from other Trusted Accounts:** Find a few accounts working to support and encourage parents and kids in their faith, and share them to your stories or repost them only be sure to credit and tag the original poster.

Other engagements include:

1. **Creating Relevant and Engaging Content:** Utilizing various forms of media such as images, videos, posts, and podcasts can also enhance engagement. In addition, it will also make the message more accessible to a wider audience.
2. **Cultivating Meaningful Relationships:** You will need to intentionally engage with Christians and non-Christians on social media to share the Gospel with them. By intentionally engaging in conversations, responding to comments, and expressing empathy, Christians can develop meaningful connections
3. **Sharing Resources and Inviting Engagement:** Different resources like articles, e-book, storybooks can be shared via social media which will encourage the online children's community to participate through question sessions, life experience issues, counselling sessions, and so on.

Challenges/Pitfalls of Using Social Media for Children Evangelism

Some of the challenges/Pitfalls that can be associated with the use of social media are as follows:

1. **Privacy and Data Security Concerns:** One of the biggest concerns with using AI in children's evangelism is the collection and handling of personal data. AI tools may require access to children's data, such as their learning preferences, behaviour, and even personal beliefs, which raises serious privacy and security concerns. Mismanagement of this data could expose children to risks such as identity theft or exploitation.
2. **Over-Reliance on Technology:** While AI can enhance learning, there is a risk that children may become overly dependent on technology for their religious education. This could undermine the importance of face-to-face interactions with religious leaders, peers, and families, which are vital for emotional and spiritual development. In-person fellowship fosters deeper, more meaningful connections that AI cannot replicate.
3. **Ethical and Theological Considerations:** AI may raise questions about the authenticity and integrity of religious teaching. Who programs the AI? How do they ensure the content aligns with specific religious traditions or doctrines? There is a risk that AI-driven content may be manipulated or misrepresented, potentially spreading distorted teachings. Children might not have the critical thinking skills to discern this.

4. Inadequate Emotional Intelligence: While AI systems can simulate conversation and interaction, they lack true emotional intelligence and understanding. Children might form attachments to AI programs, but these programs cannot offer the empathy, guidance, and care that a human mentor or spiritual leader can provide. Over-reliance on AI could deprive children of the genuine emotional and spiritual support they need.

5. Lack of Personal Connection and Community: Evangelism, at its core, is about building a community and personal connections within a faith. AI, by its nature, cannot replace the sense of belonging those physical churches, youth groups, or community outreach provide. The use of AI tools in children's evangelism might inadvertently isolate children from real-life religious communities, weakening the sense of fellowship that is central to many faiths.

6. Cultural and Religious Sensitivity: While AI can be programmed to recognize cultural and religious diversity, it might still miss nuances in how different cultures approach religious practices. AI's generalizations might not accurately reflect the diversity within and among religious traditions, leading to oversimplifications or misrepresentations of faith practices.

7. Too much reliance on AI agents like Siri, Alexa, or ChatGPT can have some implications for children's social development: According to YING XU Children learn social etiquette through interactions with others who model socially appropriate behaviours. But AI does not always follow our social norms, or encourage the use of polite language. He has observed instances where children give demands, or even insult AI (Ying Xu, 2024).

8. Children can be easily distracted and switch to other programmes focusing on what is trending on social media rather than the Christian programme that is ongoing.

9. AI can become a quick fix to sermon preparation rather than the thoughtful, prayerful study of God's Word, thereby substituting technology for the moving of the Spirit and personal relationships.

10. Evaluation/Credibility of Information: Since the rise of the internet and social media a couple of decades ago, children have increasingly faced challenges in evaluating credible information sources even adults are having trouble evaluating AI-generated information. But generative AI and ChatGPT make things a little bit more complicated whereby finding it difficult to know the source of the information.

Safety Considerations for Children's Evangelism on Social Media

- 1. Ensuring Spiritual Depth and Substance:** The Christian communities should ensure that AI supplements human effort, rather than replacing it. The church should strike a balance between AI-enhanced and traditional evangelism methods.
- 2. Age-appropriate Content:** There must be concerns about children's developmental readiness to be active online
- 3. Collaborate with Experts:** There must be collaboration with theologians, educators, and AI experts to develop effective AI-enhanced evangelism.
- 4. Monitoring and Moderation:** There must be a continuous system put in place to assess AI systems' effectiveness and impact.
- 5. Parental and Caregiver Involvement:** Encourage parental involvement in AI-enhanced evangelism. The consent and guidance for young internet users must come from parents, teachers, governments, and the social media industry.
- 6. Foster Critical Thinking:** Teach children to critically evaluate AI-generated content.
- 7. Emphasize Relationships:** Prioritize human relationships and community building.
- 8. Online Safety Guidelines:** Online Christian programmes must follow safety guidelines. This will help to overcome age misrepresentation though some children simply supply a fake age when setting up their account. We need to see increased user protection (such as age verification measures).
- 9. Transparency and Accountability:** Regularly review AI systems for bias and error.

10. **Safety and Security:** Implement robust security measures to protect children's data.

Conclusion

AI can have a positive impact on children because it significantly broadens children's access to knowledge, information, communication, and friendship. Notably, AI has become increasingly prevalent while children pastors, mentors, and teachers are recognizing their potential to enhance their ministry and to help them engage with their congregation in new and innovative ways. This paper calls for action in modern Christianity to utilize social media for children's evangelism. The potential of social media for reaching and disciplining children should not replace the traditional evangelistic methods in churches but rather enhance their leverage on the Holy Spirit as the bedrock for the conviction of the souls of men. However, social media can also have many negative effects on teenagers, both mentally and physically. Therefore, it is important to use AI ethical considerations that align with biblical values and principles that will not harm the children or violate their privacy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Adequate evangelism can only be achieved through the use/utilization of Artificial Intelligence because house-to-house evangelism may not be sufficient to achieve global evangelism.
2. Artificial Intelligence has enormous benefits as far as children evangelism is concerned but at the same time, it must be thoroughly monitored in order not to be abused by children.
3. Personal evangelism should not be ruled out completely because children believe in what I see, I remember.
4. Artificial Intelligence ethical considerations must be employed in order not to expose the children to mental and moral harm.

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